

Bio inspired technique for controlling angle of attack of aircraft

Subhakanta Bal¹, Srinibash Swain², Partha Sarathi Khuntia³

¹Department of Electrical Engineering, Bijupattnaik University of Technology, Rourkela, India

²Department of Electrical Engineering, Nalanda Institute of Technology, Bhubaneswar, India

³Department of Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering, Konark Institute of Science and Technology, Khurda, India

Article Info

Article history:

Received Jan 23, 2024

Revised Jun 11, 2024

Accepted Jun 14, 2024

Keywords:

Genetic algorithm

Mean square error

Particle swarm optimization

Proportional–integral

Teaching learning-based

optimization

ABSTRACT

This paper deals with the design of a proportional–integral (PI) controller for controlling the angle of attack of flight control system. For the first time teaching learning-based optimization (TLBO) algorithm is applied in this area to obtain the parameters of the proposed PI controller. The design problem is formulated as an optimization problem and TLBO is employed to optimize the parameters of the PI controller. The superiority of proposed approach is demonstrated by comparing the results with that of the conventional methods like genetic algorithm (GA) and particle swarm optimization (PSO). It is observed that TLBO optimized PI controller gives better dynamic performance in terms of settling time, overshoot, and undershoot as compared to GA and PSO based PI controllers. The various performance indices like mean square error (MSE), integral absolute error (IAE), and integral time absolute error (ITAE) are improved by using the TLBO soft computing techniques. Further, robustness of the system is studied by varying all the system parameters from –50% to +50% in step of 25%. Analysis also reveals that TLBO optimized PI controller gains are quite robust and need not be reset for wide variation in system parameters.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Subhakanta Bal

Department of Electrical Engineering, Bijupattnaik University of Technology

Rourkela, Odisha, India

Email: bal.subhakanta@gmail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

For smooth flying of an aircraft, managing of three controlling surfaces viz rudder, elevator, and aileron becomes inevitable. The movement of a flight is controlled by the help of above three surfaces about the pitch, roll, and yaw axes. For the orientation of aircraft, elevator performs an essential position in changing the angle of attack along with pitch. Different soft computing techniques like fuzzy model reference learning (FMRL) and radial basis function neural controller (RBFNC) are applied previously for obtaining a better result for a dynamic system. But a new soft computing technique named teaching learning-based optimization (TLBO) is incorporated in this paper mainly for adjusting the angle of attack as well as upgrading the overall achievement of the proposed system. Finally, a comparison is made between the results of TLBO and other optimization methods like genetic algorithm (GA) and particle swarm optimization (PSO) in each and every aspect.

Literature survey reveals most of the early works on flight control system. The selection of gain of a proportional–integral (PI) controller for nonlinear second order plants was suggested by Kumar *et al.* [1] in an organized manner. The regulating of a PI controller for a control system was verified by Xiang *et al.* [2] in a number of ways. A better proposal was proposed by Saxena and Hote [3] for determining the gain of a PI controller. An easy and quick method for tuning a proportional–integral–derivative (PID) controller was jointly

analyzed by Ghany *et al.* [4] in a precise manner. The various types of methods needed for estimating the angle of attack of a flight were clearly described by Sankaralingam and Ramprasadh [5]. Two-stage TLBO method for flexible job-shop scheduling was suggested by Buddala and Mahapatra [6]. Suganthi *et al.* [7] proposed an improved TLBO algorithm. Niu *et al.* [8] suggested a modified TLBO algorithm for numerical function optimization. Shahrouzi *et al.* [9] suggested a hybrid bat algorithm and TLBO.

Zhai *et al.* [10] proposed a novel TLBO with error correction for path planning of unmanned air vehicle. Zhang *et al.* [11] suggested an improved TLBO with logarithmic spiral and triangular mutation for global optimization. Nayak *et al.* [12] proposed an Elitist teaching–learning-based optimization (ETLBO) with higher-order Jordan Pi-sigma neural network. Yang *et al.* [13] proposed a multiobjective GA on an accelerator lattice. In addition, Gaing [14] proposed a PSO method to solve the economic dispatch. Evtushenko and Posypkin [15] suggested a new method in 2013 for global box-constrained optimization. Yassami and Ashtari [16] proposed a novel hybrid optimization algorithm. Storn and Price [17] proposed a differential evolution for global optimization over continuous spaces. A fuzzy adaptive differential evolution algorithm, on soft computing was suggested by. Liu and Lampinen [18]. Several researchers proposed on ant colony optimization [19], [20].

Placement of wind turbines using GA was suggested by Grady *et al.* [21]. Graphic processing unit (GPU)-based parallel PSO was proposed by Zhou and Tan [22]. A survey on new generation metaheuristic algorithms was jointly suggested in 2019 by Dokeroglu *et al.* [23]. Hussain *et al.* [24] did a comprehensive survey on artificial intelligence review. Various works on PSO using different techniques were proposed in [25]–[28]. PSO-based memetic algorithm for flow shop scheduling was suggested by Liu *et al.* [29]. Yang *et al.* [30] suggested an improved PSO-based charging strategy of electric vehicles in electrical distribution grid. This paper shows a better result by applying TLBO method for managing the attacking angle of an air craft system. After comparison the results between TLBO, GA and PSO methods, it was found that TLBO performs better in all aspects than GA and PSO methods for tuning the PID controller.

2. BLOCK DIAGRAM FOR DETERMINING THE ANGLE OF ATTACK

Figure 1 shows the block diagram for controlling the angle of attack of an aircraft. The intended angle of attack (α) is the output. The elevator's deflection (δ_E) serves as the input.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of angle of attack for an aircraft system

where $\delta_E(s)$ is the deflection angle of elevator, $\alpha(s)$ is angle of attack of the aircraft, $G(s)$ is the forward path gain, and $C(s)$ is proposed PI controller.

3. RELATION BETWEEN THE ELEVATOR DEFLECTION (δ_E) AND ANGLE OF ATTACK (α)

Generally, angle of attack is the angle between relative wind and the chord line of the aircraft. The angle of attack is obtained due to the deflection in control surface (elevator) is exhibited in Figure 2. Aircraft speed (u), is changed due to the deflection in control surfaces and atmospheric turbulence. Mainly the approximation relating to short period deals with varying flight speed (u) and it consists of very short duration. The speed of the aircraft U_0 almost remains constant throughout the process i.e., $\dot{u} = 0$. So that the motion related equation involving ' u ' is generally neglected. Hence the equations for longitudinal motion may be dictated as:

$$\dot{\mathbf{w}} = \mathbf{Z}_w \mathbf{w} + \mathbf{U}_0 \mathbf{q} + \mathbf{Z}_{\delta_s} \delta_E \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{q} &= M_{\dot{w}}\dot{w} + M_w\ddot{w} + M_q q + M_{\delta_E} \delta_E \\ &= (M_{\dot{w}} + M_w Z_w)\dot{w} + (M_q + U_0 M_w)q + (M_{\delta_E} + Z_{\delta_E} M_w)\delta_E \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Figure 2. Description of angle of attack

Calculation of state vector for short period motion may be written as:

$$x = \begin{bmatrix} w \\ q \end{bmatrix}$$

where δ_E and 'u' are the angle of deflection and control vector respectively, then the state equation for the above two equations can be written as:

$$\dot{x} = Ax + Bu \quad (3)$$

where as:

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \begin{bmatrix} Z_w & U_0 \\ (M_w + M_{\dot{w}}Z_w) & (M_q + U_0 M_w) \end{bmatrix}, B = \begin{bmatrix} Z_{\delta_E} \\ M_{\delta_E} + Z_{\delta_E} M_w \end{bmatrix} \\ \therefore [sI - A] &= s \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} Z_w & U_0 \\ (M_w + M_{\dot{w}}Z_w) & (M_q + U_0 M_w) \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} s & 0 \\ 0 & s \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} Z_w & U_0 \\ (M_w + M_{\dot{w}}Z_w) & (M_q + U_0 M_w) \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} s - Z_w & -U_0 \\ -(M_w + M_{\dot{w}}Z_w) & [s - (M_q + U_0 M_w)] \end{bmatrix} \\ \Delta_{sp}(s) &= \det[sI - A] \\ &= s^2 + [-(Z_w + M_q + U_0 M_w)]s + [Z_w M_q - U_0 M_w] \\ &= s^2 + 2\zeta_{sp}\omega_{sp}s + \omega_{sp}^2 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

In (4):

$$\begin{aligned} 2\zeta_{sp}\omega_{sp} &= -(Z_w + M_q + U_0 M_w), \\ \omega_{sp} &= [Z_w M_q - U_0 M_w]^{\frac{1}{2}} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{w(s)}{\delta_E(s)} &= \frac{(U_0 M_{\delta_E} + M_q Z_{\delta_E}) \left\{ 1 + \frac{Z_{\delta_E}}{U_0 M_{\delta_E} - M_q Z_{\delta_E}} s \right\}}{\Delta_{sp}(s)} \\ &= \frac{K_w(1+sT_1)}{\Delta_{sp}(s)} \quad \text{where:} \end{aligned}$$

$$K_w = (U_0 M_{\delta_E} + M_q Z_{\delta_E}) \text{ and } T_1 = \frac{Z_{\delta_E}}{K_w}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Again, } \dot{\alpha} &= \frac{\dot{w}}{U_0} \\
 \Rightarrow \alpha(s) &= \frac{w(s)}{U_0} \\
 \Rightarrow w(s) &= U_0 \alpha(s) \\
 \Rightarrow \frac{\alpha(s)}{\delta_E(s)} &= \frac{K_W(1+sT_1)}{U_0 \Delta_{sp}(s)} \tag{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.1. Stability derivatives of aircraft

The standard values of stability derivatives for CHARLIE aircraft in three different conditions are depicted in Table 1. These are intended for the aircraft's longitudinal dynamics. The transfer function for a specific flight condition can be found using stability derivatives.

Table 1. Stability derivatives of aircraft for three distinct flight conditions [31]

	Flight condition		
	FC-1	FC-2	FC-3
$U_0 (ms^{-1})$	67	158	250
$X_{\dot{u}}$	-0.021	0.003	-0.00002
X_w	0.122	0.078	0.026
X_{δ_E}	0.292	0.616	0.0
Z_w	-0.512	-0.433	-0.624
Z_q	-1.9	-1.95	-3.04
Z_{δ_E}	-1.96	-5.15	-8.05
M_w	-0.006	-0.006	-0.005
M_q	-0.357	-0.421	-0.668
M_{δ_E}	-0.378	-1.09	-2.08

3.2. Transfer functions of different flight conditions

Table 2 show the transfer function for FC-1, FC-2, and FC-3 respectively. FC stands for flight condition. FC-1, FC-2, and FC-3 in Table 2 can be obtained by putting the parametric values from Table 1 in (6).

Table 2. Transfer functions for three different flight conditions

Flight conditions	G(S)
FC-1	$G_1(S) = \frac{0.04936S + 0.65835}{1.695S^2 + 2.1546S + 1}$
FC-2	$G_1(S) = \frac{0.8849S^2 + 1.59469S + 1}{0.0128S + 0.978}$
FC-3	$G_3(S) = \frac{0.599S^2 + 1.525S + 1}{0.0193S + 1.26}$

4. PROPOSED OPTIMIZATION SOFT COMPUTING TECHNIQUES

There are so many methods for determining the gain of PI controller. Among them GA and PSO methods are applied here for tuning the controller. Numerous optimization techniques have been used to address the different kinds of real-world issues in various sectors. The TLBO approach is thought to be superior to the rest among them.

4.1. Teaching learning-based optimization

Following its introduction by Rao *et al.* [32], TLBO has gained a lot of popularity in the engineering domain. Its stability analysis, time consumption, and solution quality are superior than those of other methods. In general, TLBO operates in two stages: In the first stage, known as the teacher phase, students learned from their individual teachers; in the second stage, known as the learner phase, students learn from one another through interaction. The following steps are part of the TLBO algorithm.

4.1.1. Initialization

The population size is taken as [NP D]. In this case NP indicates size of population i.e. number of learners and D indicates the dimension of the problem i.e. number of subjects offered. The *i*th column of the initial population represents the marks secured by different learners in *i*th subject.

$$\text{Initial population} = \begin{matrix} x_{1,1} & x_{1,2} & \dots & x_{1,D} \\ x_{2,1} & x_{2,2} & \dots & x_{2,D} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_{NP,1} & x_{NP,2} & \dots & x_{NP,D} \end{matrix}$$

4.1.2. Teacher phase

During this phase, the designated instructor puts up their best effort to raise the class mean. Since teachers are the ones who train the students, the best learner's solution always goes to that specific teacher. The average grades obtained by various pupils in various assignments are computed (7).

$$M_d = [m_1, m_2, \dots, m_D] \tag{7}$$

whereas m_1 is the aggregate marks secured by the students in i th paper. The dissimilarity in mean results of a particular teacher is represented as $M_{diff} = rand(0,1)[X_{best} - T_F M_d]$. In which $rand(0,1)$ is chosen arbitrarily as 0 or 1 and T_F as teaching factor. T_F is taken arbitrarily either 1 or 2.

$$T_F = round[1 + rand(0,1)] \tag{8}$$

In (9) the exiting population is renewed as (9):

$$X_{new} = X + M_{diff} \tag{9}$$

X_{new} is accepted if $(X_{new}) < f(X)$, where $f(X)$ is taken as the objective function.

4.1.3. Learner phase

In this case, the teacher chooses a student at random through contact in order to advance their knowledge. If other pupils are more knowledgeable than him, then he can effectively learn more from them through interaction. The steps involved in learning stage are as follows. Randomly select two learners X_i and X_j such that $i \neq j$.

$$X_{new} = X_i + rand(0,1)(X_i - X_j). \quad \text{If}(X_j) < f(X_j) \tag{10}$$

$X_{new} = X_i + rand(0,1)(X_j - X_i)$. Take X_{new} as granted if better performance is found.

5. SIMULATION RESULT

In this part, TLBO technique is used for designing the best variables of a PI system employing the transfer function of first flight condition. A comparison is made between TLBO with PI and conventional methods for comparing the advantages of proposed controllers. Step responses of the flight control system employing TLBO-PI, GA and PSO methods are obtained by varying three different parameters from -50% to +50% are shown from Figures 3 to 14. Similar figures can also be drawn by varying the remaining parameters. It is evident from these figures that settling time of the suggested TLBO approach is lower in comparison to PSO and GA procedures.

Figure 3. Deviation of Z_w by -50%

Figure 4. Deviation of Z_w by -25%

Figure 5. Deviation of Z_w by +25%

Figure 6. Deviation of Z_w by +50%

Figure 7. Deviation of M_q by -50%

Figure 8. Deviation of M_q by -25%

Figure 9. Deviation of M_q by +25%

Figure 10. Deviations of M_q by +50%

Figure 11. Deviation of Mw by -50%

Figure 12. Deviation of Mw by -25%

Figure 13. Deviation of Mw by +25%

Figure 14. Deviation of Mw by +50%

6. ROBUSTNESS ANALYSIS

For testing the toughness of the CHARLIE Aircraft, the parameters are changed from -50% to +50%. Then robustness is measured by using the optimum values obtained from TLBO optimized PI controller. A comparison results among GA, PSO and TLBO are also depicted in Table 3 and 4 respectively. Different analysis results related to integral absolute error (IAE), integral time absolute error (ITAE), and mean square error (MSE), settling time, peak under-shoots and peak overshoots are given in these tables. Now it is obvious that the proposed technique is quite powerful when subjected to a large range of parametric variation. But also retuning of controller parameters does not necessary over the wide range. Similarly, the performance indices obtained from TLBO is less than that obtained from conventional methods like GA and PSO.

Table 3. Variation of settling time, under shoot, and over shoot, IAE, ITAE, and MSE for GA and TLBO

Deviation of parameters (%)	GA						TLBO					
	Ts	Ush	Osh	IAE	ITAE	MSE	Ts	Ush	Osh	IAE	ITAE	MSE
-50	8.27	30.86	12.4	1.1	2.56	0.5	3.9	75.47	35.4	0.7	0.7	0.3
-25	13.9	40.14	19.9	1.1	5	0.6	3.51	57.55	27.7	0.8	1	0.4
+25	21.6	74.62	36.8	1.5	6.5	0.7	6.8	79.93	40.5	1.3	2.5	0.5
+50	22.3	84	46.6	1.7	6.9	0.8	8.4	38.9	48.5	1.4	4	0.6

Table 4. Variation of settling time, under shoot, and over shoot, IAE, ITAE, and MSE for PSO and TLBO

Deviation of parameters (%)	PSO						TLBO					
	Ts	Ush	Osh	IAE	ITAE	MSE	Ts	Ush	Osh	IAE	ITAE	MSE
-50	5.56	61.8	29	1	1.3	0.4	3.9	75.47	35.4	0.7	0.7	0.3
-25	3.8	52.8	26.4	0.9	1.2	0.5	3.51	57.55	27.7	0.8	1	0.4
+25	8.4	76.61	37.6	1.4	2.7	0.6	6.8	79.93	40.5	1.3	2.5	0.5
+50	9.42	86	47.3	1.6	4.3	0.7	8.4	38.9	48.5	1.4	4	0.6

The above comparison values are also displayed in form of bar charts from Figures 15 to 18. Thus, the analysis shows better result for TLBO optimized PI controller than PSO and GA methods. In Table 5 to 7, variation of performance indices like ITAE, MSE, and IAE are demonstrated.

Figure 15. IAE among TLBO, PSO, and GA

Figure 16. MSE among TLBO, PSO, and GA

Figure 17. Ts among TLBO, PSO, and GA

Figure 18. ITAE among TLBO, PSO, and GA

Table 5. Variation of IAE, ITAE, and MSE

Parameters	%Deviation	GA			PSO			TLBO		
		IAE	ITAE	MSE	IAE	ITAE	MSE	IAE	ITAE	MSE
Z_w	-50	1.23	7.04	0.29	0.88	2.16	0.34	0.83	1.04	0.27
	-25	1.22	6.6	0.31	0.89	1.85	0.36	0.88	1.18	0.30
	+25	1.23	5.56	0.36	1.05	1.82	0.44	1.04	1.68	0.33
	+50	1.24	4.98	0.39	1.24	2.45	0.51	1.11	2.40	0.37
M_q	-50	1.25	7.11	0.31	0.89	2.07	0.35	0.86	1.14	0.30
	-25	1.24	6.63	0.32	0.91	1.86	0.37	0.90	1.25	0.31
	+25	1.21	5.62	0.35	1.02	1.74	0.43	1.01	1.62	0.34
	+50	1.20	5.05	0.37	1.12	1.96	0.47	1.08	1.83	0.35
U_0	-50	1.01	1.86	0.44	2.12	7.18	0.83	0.82	1.04	0.34
	-25	1.11	4.08	0.37	1.13	1.92	0.49	0.99	1.53	0.36
	+25	1.27	7.29	0.41	0.97	2.82	0.35	0.44	1.37	0.32
	+50	1.26	7.82	0.28	1.40	4.18	0.32	1.05	3.04	0.37
M_w	-50	1.36	8.30	0.41	1.03	2.51	0.35	0.94	1.61	0.31
	-25	1.29	7.25	0.42	0.96	2.03	0.37	0.93	1.37	0.33
	+25	1.16	5.01	0.40	1.03	1.70	0.43	1.02	1.63	0.35
	+50	1.12	3.93	0.38	1.17	2.08	0.49	1.05	1.98	0.37
$M_{\delta E}$	-50	1.09	5.00	0.41	0.94	1.83	0.37	0.93	1.79	0.31
	-25	1.15	5.49	0.42	0.95	1.78	0.38	0.94	1.15	0.32
	+25	1.34	7.04	0.41	0.97	1.68	0.42	0.96	1.40	0.36
	+50	1.45	8.27	0.42	0.99	1.58	0.47	0.97	1.45	0.35
$Z_{\delta E}$	-50	1.15	4.73	0.37	1.03	1.55	0.46	0.82	1.08	0.36
	-25	1.20	5.48	0.38	0.96	1.46	0.43	0.88	1.22	0.35
	+25	1.21	6.36	0.36	1.17	2.51	0.37	0.99	2.07	0.32
	+50	1.13	5.77	0.37	1.08	3.72	0.34	1.06	2.47	0.33

Table 6. Variation of settling time, under shoot, and over shoot

Parameters	%Deviation	GA			PSO			TLBO		
		Ts	Ush	Osh	Ts	Ush	Osh	Ts	Ush	Osh
Z_w	-50	23.9	16.67	24	6.16	16.88	24	4.32	20.10	23.9
	-25	21.1	17.54	26	6	18.3	27	5.62	21.26	25.6
	+25	16	18.98	30.5	6.36	21.11	34.8	5.77	22.74	34.2
	+50	13.5	19.86	33.4	6.71	22.27	40.4	6.28	20.89	33.1
M_q	-50	23.5	17.23	25.2	6.07	17.73	25.6	5.58	20.67	25.1
	-25	20.9	17.61	26.6	6.04	18.19	27.8	5.69	21.48	26.2
	+25	16.4	18.93	29.8	6.29	20.48	33.6	5.84	22.88	29.6
	+50	14.1	19.18	31.7	6.52	21.72	37.2	5.82	23.17	31.5
U_0	-50	7.11	17.79	25.6	12.6	23.84	52	4.39	22.52	25.1
	-25	11.3	17.34	25.7	6.98	22.02	35.7	5.69	23.76	25.5
	+25	27	18.92	30.6	7.99	18.78	29.4	5.74	21.46	29.3
	+50	36.3	19.95	32.8	11.8	18.63	29.9	8.69	23.23	29.4
M_w	-50	27	15.97	23.5	8.03	16.1	23.3	5.66	23.47	23.2
	-25	22.8	17.05	25.7	6.15	17.78	26.6	5.66	22.36	25.5
	+25	14.4	19.43	31	6.28	21.38	35.2	5.82	23.29	30.9
	+50	10.4	20.98	34.2	6.57	23.49	40.8	6.22	21.81	33.8
$M_{\delta E}$	-50	15.4	21.6	37.2	5.18	21.99	37.9	5.1	21.76	37.1
	-25	17.1	20.4	33.3	5.56	20.9	34.6	5.25	17.1	20.4
	+25	19.9	14.93	21.4	6.75	17.47	25.4	6.33	20.02	21.3
	+50	20.8	9.02	11.7	5.04	14.2	18.7	4.81	15.56	11.6
$Z_{\delta E}$	-50	12.9	14.59	20.3	5.5	20.16	30.2	5.48	20.89	20.2
	-25	15.3	16.23	23.7	6.43	19.85	29.7	5.65	21.74	23.5
	+25	22.7	20.23	34.1	7.56	20.62	33.6	6.34	23.03	33.1
	+50	25.9	23.16	44	9.84	21.74	40.1	7.52	23.53	39.8

Table 7. Controller parameters for GA, PSO, and TLBO

Parameters	%Deviation	GA		PSO		TLBO	
		Kp	Ki	Kp	Ki	Kp	Ki
Z_w	-50	23.5	1.2	16.31	3.12	14.5	5.5
	-25	21.5	1.25	14.94	3.3	13.8	5.7
	+25	17.5	1.37	12.2	3.62	14.8	4.7
	+50	15.6	1.45	10.8	3.84	13.2	2.7
M_q	-50	22.3	1.2	15.5	3.2	14.6	5.2
	-25	20.9	1.25	14.5	3.3	13.5	4.5
	+25	18.2	1.35	12.6	3.6	12.9	5.6
	+50	16.8	1.42	11.7	3.74	14.8	4.7
U_0	-50	8.2	1.9	5.72	5.26	13.5	5.8
	-25	13.5	1.56	9.4	4.1	14.8	7.4
	+25	26.4	1.12	18.32	2.95	13.8	5.7
	+50	33.9	0.98	23.6	2.6	12.2	10.6
M_w	-50	22.6	1.21	15.7	3.2	15	10.8
	-25	21.1	1.25	14.65	3.3	14.6	7.4
	+25	18	1.35	12.5	3.6	13.9	5.8
	+50	16.5	1.42	11.43	3.74	13.2	2.72
$M_{\delta E}$	-50	19.5	1.06	13.6	2.8	13.6	2.74
	-25	19.5	1.16	13.6	3.06	0.82	0.01
	+25	19.5	1.5	13.6	3.96	13.9	5.4
	+50	19.5	1.8	13.6	4.9	14.5	5.6
$Z_{\delta E}$	-50	13	1.6	9.05	4.2	13.6	4.9
	-25	15.6	1.45	10.9	3.84	14.5	5.4
	+25	26	1.12	18.1	2.97	13.2	5.9
	+50	39.1	0.9	27.2	2.4	12.2	5.8

7. RESULT ANALYSIS

Using the Simulink platform in MATLAB 2014, the time domain simulated results of various reactions are achieved. With respect to this, the suggested flight control system model is created in the Simulink environment; however, the necessary programmes for the suggested GA, PSO, and TLBO approach are written in.m files. A step input is given for studying the behavior of a PI run flight system. Result obtained is compared with that of GA and PSO methods. It is obvious that the TLBO optimized PI managed device additionally offers higher dynamic response when subjected to a parametric change.

In Tables 3 and 4, deviation of performance indices like ITAE, MSE, and IAE are depicted along with settling time, undershoots, and overshoots. In each and every case it shows less error for IAE, ITAE, and MSE and less settling time also in TLBO optimized PI controller than that of GA and PSO. In addition to this, Tables 5 and 6 indicate the various analytical results of overshoots, settling time, undershoots, IAE, ITAE and

MSE corresponding to deviation of all parameters in four stages ranging from -50% to +50% at a stretch of 25%. These comparison values are also displayed in form of bar charts from Figures 15 to 18. Similarly, Table 7 shows the controller parameters for GA, PSO, and TLBO respectively.

Thus, the presented observations shows better result for TLBO optimized PI controller than the GA and PSO methods. Pictorial representation of overshoot, undershoot and settling time are also given from Figures 3 to 14 for verification. The above result indicates that the suggested TLBO algorithm gives better steady state output as compared to above two mentioned PI managed device.

8. CONCLUSION

To study the overall achievement of a flight control system, a PI controller is applied here along with TLBO algorithm for getting the best gain of PI controller. Then a comparison is made between GA, PSO and TLBO based PI controller for dynamic performance. A better result is achieved in TLBO managed PI controller than GA and PSO. For studying the behavior of the aircraft under various hazardous conditions, its controlling parameters are changed from -50% to +50% of nominal value in steps of 25%. Final results come in favor of TLBO and retuning of parameters is not necessary over a wide range.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Kumar, I. Kasireddy, A. Kumar, and A. K. Singh, "Estimation of stability regions of fractional PI controller for LFC of power system," in *2019 IEEE International Conference on Sustainable Energy Technologies*, 2019, pp. 313–318, doi: 10.1109/ICSETS.2019.8745072.
- [2] Z. Xiang, X. Shao, H. Wu, D. Ji, F. Yu, and Y. Li, "An adaptive integral separated proportional–integral controller based strategy for particle swarm optimization," *Knowledge-Based Systems*, vol. 195, May 2020, pp. 1–15, doi: 10.1016/j.knosys.2020.105696.
- [3] S. Saxena and Y. V Hote, "Robustly stabilizing proportional integral controller for uncertain system under computational delay," *Journal of Vibration and Control*, vol. 27, no. 19–20, pp. 2268–2278, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1177/1077546320957921.
- [4] M. A. A. Ghany, M. E. Bahgat, W. M. Refaey, and S. Sharaf, "Type-2 fuzzy self-tuning of modified fractional-order PID based on Takagi–Sugeno method," *Journal of Electrical Systems and Information Technology*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1–20, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1186/s43067-019-0009-9.
- [5] L. Sankaralingam and C. Ramprasad, "A comprehensive survey on the methods of angle of attack measurement and estimation in UAVs," *Chinese Journal of Aeronautics*, vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 749–770, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.cja.2019.11.003.
- [6] R. Buddala and S. S. Mahapatra, "Two-stage teaching-learning-based optimization method for flexible job-shop scheduling under machine breakdown," *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, vol. 100, no. 5–8, 2019, doi: 10.1007/s00170-018-2805-0.
- [7] S.T. Suganthi, D. Devaraj, S.H. Thilagar, and K. Ramar, "Optimal generator rescheduling with distributed slack bus model for congestion management using improved teaching learning based optimization algorithm," *Sādhanā*, vol. 43, no. 11, 2018, doi: 10.1007/s12046-018-0941-8.
- [8] P. Niu, Y. Ma, and S. Yan, "A modified teaching–learning-based optimization algorithm for numerical function optimization," *International Journal of Machine Learning and Cybernetics*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 1357–1371, Jun. 2019, doi: 10.1007/s13042-018-0815-8.
- [9] M. Shahrrouzi, F. R. -Alavijeh, and M. Aghabaglou, "Configuration design of structures under dynamic constraints by a hybrid bat algorithm and teaching–learning based optimization," *International Journal of Dynamics and Control*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 419–429, Jun. 2019, doi: 10.1007/s40435-018-0455-6.
- [10] Z. Zhai, G. Jia, and K. Wang, "A novel teaching-learning-based optimization with error correction and cauchy distribution for path planning of unmanned air vehicle," *Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience*, vol. 2018, no. 3, pp. 1–12, Aug. 2018, doi: 10.1155/2018/5671709.
- [11] Z. Zhang, H. Huang, C. Huang, and B. Han, "An improved TLBO with logarithmic spiral and triangular mutation for global optimization," *Neural Computing and Applications*, vol. 31, no. 8, pp. 4435–4450, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.1007/s00521-018-3785-6.
- [12] J. Nayak, B. Naik, H. S. Behera, and A. Abraham, "Elitist teaching–learning-based optimization (ETLBO) with higher-order Jordan Pi-sigma neural network: a comparative performance analysis," *Neural Computing and Applications*, vol. 30, no. 5, pp. 1445–1468, Sep. 2018, doi: 10.1007/s00521-016-2738-1.
- [13] L. Yang, D. Robin, F. Sannibale, C. Steier, and W. Wan, "Global optimization of an accelerator lattice using multiobjective genetic algorithms," *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, vol. 609, no. 1, pp. 50–57, Oct. 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.nima.2009.08.027.
- [14] Z. -L. Gaing, "Particle swarm optimization to solving the economic dispatch considering the generator constraints," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 1187–1195, Aug. 2003, doi: 10.1109/TPWRS.2003.814889.
- [15] Y. Evtushenko and M. Posypkin, "A deterministic approach to global box-constrained optimization," *Optimization Letters*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 819–829, Apr. 2013, doi: 10.1007/s11590-012-0452-1.
- [16] M. Yassami and P. Ashtari, "A novel hybrid optimization algorithm: Dynamic hybrid optimization algorithm," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, vol. 82, no. 21, pp. 31947–31979, Sep. 2023, doi: 10.1007/s11042-023-14444-8.
- [17] R. Storn and K. Price, "Differential evolution—a simple and efficient heuristic for global optimization over continuous spaces," *Journal of Global Optimization*, vol. 11, pp. 341–359, 1997.
- [18] J. Liu and J. Lampinen, "A fuzzy adaptive differential evolution algorithm," *Soft Computing*, vol. 9, no. 6, 2005, doi: 10.1007/s00500-004-0363-x.
- [19] M. Dorigo, M. Birattari, and T. Stutzle, "Ant colony optimization," *IEEE Computational Intelligence Magazine*, vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 28–39, Nov. 2006, doi: 10.1109/MCI.2006.329691.
- [20] K. Socha and M. Dorigo, "Ant colony optimization for continuous domains," *European Journal of Operational Research*, vol. 185, no. 3, pp. 1155–1173, Mar. 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.ejor.2006.06.046.
- [21] S. A. Grady, M. Y. Hussaini, and M. M. Abdullah, "Placement of wind turbines using genetic algorithms," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 30, no. 2, pp. 259–270, Feb. 2005, doi: 10.1016/j.renene.2004.05.007.

- [22] Y. Zhou and Y. Tan, "GPU-based parallel particle swarm optimization," in *2009 IEEE Congress on Evolutionary Computation*, May 2009, pp. 1493–1500. doi: 10.1109/CEC.2009.4983119.
- [23] T. Dokeroglu, E. Sevinc, T. Kucukyilmaz, and A. Cosar, "A survey on new generation metaheuristic algorithms," *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, vol. 137, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.cie.2019.106040.
- [24] K. Hussain, M. N. Mohd Salleh, S. Cheng, and Y. Shi, "Metaheuristic research: a comprehensive survey," *Artificial Intelligence Review*, vol. 52, no. 4, pp. 2191–2233, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.1007/s10462-017-9605-z.
- [25] A. A. D. M. Meneses, M. D. Machado, and R. Schirru, "Particle swarm optimization applied to the nuclear reload problem of a pressurized water reactor," *Progress in Nuclear Energy*, vol. 51, no. 2, pp. 319–326, Mar. 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.pnucene.2008.07.002.
- [26] H. Fang *et al.*, "Hybrid method integrating machine learning and particle swarm optimization for smart chemical process operations," *Frontiers of Chemical Science and Engineering*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 274–287, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s11705-021-2043-0.
- [27] Y. Marinakis, M. Marinaki, and G. Dounias, "Particle swarm optimization for pap-smear diagnosis," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 35, no. 4, pp. 1645–1656, Nov. 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.eswa.2007.08.089.
- [28] J. -B. Park, Y. -W. Jeong, J. -R. Shin, and K. Y. Lee, "An improved particle Swarm optimization for nonconvex economic dispatch problems," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 156–166, Feb. 2010, doi: 10.1109/TPWRS.2009.2030293.
- [29] B. Liu, L. Wang, and Y.-H. Jin, "An effective PSO-based memetic algorithm for fow shop scheduling," *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man and Cybernetics, Part B (Cybernetics)*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 18–27, Feb. 2007, doi: 10.1109/TSMCB.2006.883272.
- [30] J. Yang, L. He, and S. Fu, "An improved PSO-based charging strategy of electric vehicles in electrical distribution grid," *Applied Energy*, vol. 128, pp. 82–92, Sep. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2014.04.047.
- [31] D. McLean, *Automatic flight control system*, Cambridge, United Kingdom: Prentice Hall International, 1990.
- [32] R.V. Rao, V. J. Savsani, and D. P. Vakharia, "Teaching–learning-based optimization: an optimization method for continuous non-linear large scale problems," *Information Sciences*, vol. 183, no. 1, pp. 1–15, Jan. 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.ins.2011.08.006.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Mr. Subhakanta Bal was born on 5th July 1968 in Odisha, India. He completed his M.Tech. degree in Power Electronics & Drives in 2012 from SOA University, BBSR, Odisha India. Now he is continuing his Ph. D degree in BPUT, Rourkela, Odish, India. His major field of study is control system analysis and design. He is now working as Assistant Professor in Synergy Institute of Technology, BBSR since last eight years. He has published three papers in international journals. His current research interest is soft computing application in the field of control system. He is a life member in ISTE. He is also a senior member in Institution of Engineers, India. He can be contacted at email: bal.subhakanta@gmail.com.

Mr. Srinibash Swain was born on 21st May 1970 in Odisha, India. He completed his M.E. degree in Power System Engineering in 2001 from VSSUT, Burla, Odisha, India. He has completed his Ph.D. degree in BPUT, Rourkela, and Odisha, India in 2019. His major field of study is control system analysis and design. He is now working as Professor in Rajdhani Engineering College, BBSR since last one year. He has published five papers in international journals. His current research interest is soft computing application in the field of control system. He is a life member in ISTE. He is also a senior member in Institution of Engineers, India. He can be contacted at email: swainsrinibash@gmail.com.

Dr. Partha Sarathi Khuntia was born on 06th oct. 1969 in Odisha, India. He completed his M.E. degree in Automatic Control System and Robotics from MS University, Varodara in 1999. He has completed his Ph.D. degree from ISM Dhanbad in 2011. India. His major field of study is intelligent control, digital signal processing, and soft computing. He is now working as Professor in GMRIT, Rajam, Srikakulum, and Andhra Pradeesh. He has published many papers in national and international journals. His current research interest is advanced control theory and its application. He is a life member in ISTE. He is also a senior member in Institution of Engineers, India. Recent advances in Electrical Engineering and Computer Science ISBN. He can be contacted at email: parthsarathi_K@yahoo.com.